

H31H: Physics-Informed and Data-Driven Machine Learning Methods for Modeling Subsurface Processes I Oral

H31H-03

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08:50 – 09:00

MAR2PROTECT - Data driven models for contrasting seawater intrusion via managed aquifer recharge

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The EU faces unprecedented environmental challenges of groundwater security under the impact of **climate and global change** (CC and GC).

The EU's water-dependent sectors generate **3.4 trillion€/year**, 26% of the EU's annual gross value added, and employ around **44 million** people.

MAR2PROTECT DEMO SITES

MAR2PROTECT is a 4-year project (2022-2026) under EU Horizon2022 aimed to — Preventing groundwater contamination and protecting its quality against harmful impacts of global and climate change

Novel Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) System

CLIMATE CHANGE AND GLOBAL CHANGE

Rainfalls, floods, stormwater

Drought

Temperature Sea increase

Migration

Human activities

Industry

Agriculture

Reclaimed WW

WWTP

Estuaries

Rivers

Sea

Salt Intrusion

POLLUTANTS

N/P, pharmaceuticals, PFAS,
microplastics, pesticides

Aquifer
recharge

MAR – Managed Aquifer Recharge – natural barrier buffer capacity

GROUNDWATER

Managed Aquifer Recharge (MAR) is the most powerful tool to curb salinity intrusion and to prevent other types of GW contamination by injecting freshwater.

Challenges:

- Decision support tools for MAR in GC and CC scenarios
- Valid model-based MAR design tools
- Optimal control system for MAR

Managed Aquifer Recharge System

- **DRONE** : This Data-Driven Modeling tool will use nonstationary time series to forecast aquifer response to uncertain climate change impacts on groundwater and to support decision making for MAR system.

Data Input

Water Quality: Salinity, Nitrogen, Chlorine, ...
Water Quantity: Electrical conductivity, Rainfall, Temperature, ...

Non-stationary Data-driven Model

Non-stationary Gaussian Process to learn spatial and temporal trend and seasonal behavior of groundwater

Expected Output

Prediction for Water quantity and Water quality in the following month

- The coastal phreatic aquifer of Emilia Romagna Region (Ravenna lies in the middle) is primarily located within the littoral sand and locally in the shallow marine wedge deposits.
- 25 piezometers sensor are deployed along the coastal line, the sensor feedback the temperature and electrical conductivity data monthly.

Grid-free spatial and temporal Data for each single well

Treat the time series data as a Gaussian Process,

$$y = \mu + \mathcal{GP}(0, k(x, x'))$$

where μ represents mean and k is kernel function. The kernel function is a linear combination of stationary kernel functions k_s and non-stationary kernel functions k_{ns} .

Stationary kernel

Squared exponential

$$k_s(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \theta_1^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')^2}{2 * \theta_2^2}\right)$$

Periodic

$$k_s(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \theta_1^2 \exp\left(-\frac{(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')^2}{2 * \theta_2^2} - \frac{2 \sin^2(\pi(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'))}{\theta_3^2}\right)$$

Matérn

$$k_s(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \frac{2^{1-\theta_1}}{\Gamma(\theta_1)} \left(\frac{\sqrt{2\theta_1}|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|}{\theta_2}\right)^{\theta_1} K_{\theta_1}\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\theta_1}|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'|}{\theta_2}\right)$$

Non-stationary kernel

General Non-Stationary Kernel

$$k_{ns}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \frac{2|\Sigma|^{1/4}|\Sigma'|^{1/4}}{|\Sigma + \Sigma'|^{1/2}} k_s(\sqrt{Q(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}')})$$

Machine Learning Kernel

$$k_{NN}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \frac{2}{\pi} \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{2\mathbf{x}^T \Sigma \mathbf{x}'}{\sqrt{(1 + 2\mathbf{x}^T \Sigma \mathbf{x})(1 + 2\mathbf{x}'^T \Sigma \mathbf{x}')}}\right)$$

Non-stationary kernel on space and time [for single-well data]

Gibbs kernel function $\mathbf{x} = (t, z)$ t: time z: depth r: positive defined function

$$k_{Gibbs}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{x}') = \theta_1 \prod_{i=1}^2 \left\{ \frac{2r_i(\mathbf{x}_i; \theta)r_i(\mathbf{x}'_i; \theta)}{r_i(\mathbf{x}_i; \theta)^2 + r_i(\mathbf{x}'_i; \theta)^2} \right\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \exp\left(-\sum_{j=1}^2 \frac{(\mathbf{x}_j - \mathbf{x}'_j)^2}{r_j(\mathbf{x}_j; \theta)^2 + r_j(\mathbf{x}'_j; \theta)^2}\right)$$

Optimize hyperparameters θ_i by marginal likelihood function, K is the covariance matrix

$$\log p(\mathbf{y}|X) = -\mathbf{y}^T K^{-1} \mathbf{y} - \frac{1}{2} \log |K| - \frac{n}{2} \log 2\pi$$

Gaussian kernel function on GIS map [for multiple wells]

Gaussian kernel function with GIS norm

$$\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}'\|_{GIS}^2 = \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_1 - \mathbf{X}'_1\|_{distance}^2}{\theta_1^2} + \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_2 - \mathbf{X}'_2\|_{altitude}^2}{\theta_2^2} + \frac{\|\mathbf{X}_3 - \mathbf{X}'_3\|_{others}^2}{\theta_3^2}$$

Optimize linear coefficient of Gaussian kernel function, y_j denoted as single well GP model

$$Y(\mathbf{X}) = \sum_j v \exp\left(-\frac{\|\mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_j\|_{GIS}^2}{l^2}\right) y_j$$

Single Well Results for Four Selected Locations

Red points are the training set, blue points are the testing set. The figure positions are San Giuseppe, Porto Corsini, Punta Marina, Taglio Nuovo

Electrical conductivity EC (mS/cm) in aquifer at a depth of -3.5 meters

The prediction is on Jun, 2021, Apr, 2022 and Mar 2023 respectively. The prediction is generated by non-stationary Gaussian process. When $EC > 30$, it is saltwater. With $10 < EC < 30$ mS/cm, it is brackish water, when $EC < 10$ mS/cm, it is freshwater

Building up Physical-Inform neural network to predict the effects of MAR

Data Inputs

Electrical
Conductivity

Rainfall

Sea level

Ammonia

Machine learning model

Without valid physical model

Data assimilation method

With valid physical model^[1]

Prediction of GW quality and quantity in a phreatic aquifer

[1] Ward J, Dillon P. Robust design of managed aquifer recharge policy in Australia[J].

Conclusions

- The non-stationary Gaussian Process model better captures the characteristics of time series compared to stationary training (Felisa et al., Data-driven models of groundwater salinization in coastal plains, *J. Hydrol.*, 2015).

A general map system based on GIS norm can provide a prediction on a large scale.

A challenge will be to incorporate anthropogenic effects such as groundwater recharge and boundary conditions such as sea level into the model without/with physical model

Next stage

Insert physical model of MAR into machine learning model to predict the effect on coastal aquifer

Thank you for your attention

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